

The content of the formation of an acmeological position in future teachers

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Annotation: the content of the formation of an acmeological position in future teachers in this article is based on the possibilities and existing situations in the process of improving the requirements for modern teachers, training specialists in pedagogical universities, the processes of introduction of innovative technologies into the teaching system in these educational institutions were tried to reveal as a problem of the topic.

Keywords: Acmeology, position, Content, students, innovative methods, modern information technology, assimilation of knowledge, skills and qualifications of future teachers, professional training.

The formation of the educational system of the new Uzbekistan and the socio-economic policy corresponding to the market economy – requires the formation of an acmeological position in future teachers who meet the requirements of the time, train highly qualified specialist personnel and ensure the effectiveness of this process.

Therefore, today the practical provision of the educational process of continuing education institutions, in particular higher education institutions, with a new and modern methodology based on advanced, scientific-theoretical, has been identified as one of the pressing problems waiting for a solution in this area, ensuring the deep development of youth skills and qualifications of our country, education in the chosen profession.

In fact, the main direction of strategic tasks in the field of education and education carried out in our country is characterized by the focus on the issues of training specialists who can carry out independent thinking, accurately determine the prospects for development, which will be necessary for the interests of society and the individual. This creates the need for training, modernization of pedagogical personnel and the development of its innovative pedagogical foundations.

The main content of the formation of an acmeological position in future teachers is the formation of professional training in them.

Professional training is interpreted as a specific manifestation of professional social competence, which arises on the basis of mastering the necessary professional knowledge, skills and qualifications.

Professional training does not occur on its own, but covers specific stages planned on the basis of specific goals. The formation of professional training in a person is initially determined by the content of the imagination, concepts inherent in the profession, which is later explained by the acquisition of knowledge, skills and skills related to the specialty, the decision-making of professional qualities and the level of professional adaptation.

Professional training is the level of physiological, psychological and physical training of an individual in relation to the conduct of professional activities on the basis of special theoretical knowledge, practical skills and qualifications, as well as mastering spiritual and moral qualities.

Formation of professional training-the formation of special theoretical knowledge, practical skills and qualifications in a person on the basis of the requirements of the DTS, as well as spiritual and moral qualities, is the process of physiological, psychological and physical training of the future specialist in relation to the successful conduct of professional activities.

Professional adaptation-in the context of objective and subjective education is the future professional activity of the future professional person, the assimilation of his requirements, adaptation to the process of activity, the level of professional competence.

The theoretical study of the research problem showed that organizational and pedagogical, educational and methodological and material and technical conditions in higher educational institutions, in particular in pedagogical universities, are leading factors in the process of professional adaptation.

On this basis, today a number of measures are being implemented to improve the material and technical support of pedagogical universities, expand the range of educational and methodological opportunities. However, the fact that the current content of professional adaptation of future teachers is not improved within the framework of modern requirements for the personality of a pedagogical specialist, the results of scientific research in this area are not applied to full-fledged practice, the possibilities in the process of training specialists in pedagogical universities and, based on the current state diagnostics, the full-fledged introduction of innovative technologies.

Indeed, the solution of these issues implies the goal of radical reform of the existing educational system in our republic, the formation of a highly spiritual person

through the formation of a system of continuing education. Therefore, the role of higher educational institutions is great in the upbringing of a harmonious personality, the formation of him as a specialist, the acquisition of a worthy professional and social status in society.

Based on the specificity of the system of training of pedagogical specialists of higher educational institutions, within the framework of the study, it was determined that the provision of the following pedagogical psychological conditions will serve to form an acmeological position in future teachers:

1. Informative-meaningful conditions. As you know, the content of education is a pre-designed system of professional knowledge, skills and skills that the future specialist should master, in which the course and project work associated with DTS, curricula, improved educational programs, lecture texts, educational-methodological complexes based on educational technologies, scientific and educational-methodological, electronic textbooks, control tools: creative pedagogical tasks, situational issues, remote control, creative project work, areas of expertise occupy a special place.

2. Technological conditions. The purpose of the study, that is, the technological conditions for the development and practical implementation of the process of forming an acmeological position in future teachers, was taken as the basis. In this

- problem training;
- Gaming Technologies (role-playing games, entrepreneurial games);
- training, video training;
- problematic seminars;
- solving and analyzing pedagogical problem situations, " case-stadi";
- teaching in small groups, micro-lessons;
- creative research techniques;
- methods for designing lesson and educational events;
- special attention was paid to the development of a methodology for organizing and conducting autotrenings.

The technological conditions for the formation of an acmeological position in future teachers are based on such principles as theoretical justification, a holistic approach to the content and organizational aspects of the educational and educational process, systemativeness, individuality of those educated in teaching, professional orientation of attention.

3. Reflexive conditions. Particular attention was paid to the creation of a reflexive (reflection-backward, analysis, changes, the degree to which an individual can assess his activity) environment as a result product of the created pedagogical

conditions. The content of directed reflexive conditions for the formation of an acmeological position in future teachers was defined as follows:

- development of active cognitive motivation;
- decision-making of an acmeological approach to professional activity;
- formation of creative skills;
- formation of pedagogical-psychological, methodological knowledge;
- self-awareness.

The development of society and the increasing social requirements for the education of the younger generation make the need for changes in the system of training pedagogical specialists both in terms of content and quality. Noting the relevance of this problem, our first president I.Karimov said, " We know very well how important teacher labor plays in the formation of a new generation, new thinkers in our country, the spiritual world of young people who will come to our place tomorrow.

For the teacher is the one who not only brings grace and brilliance into the classroom, but also exalts the oil of goodness in the hearts of thousands, the school of life”.

The main content of the formation of an acmeological position in future teachers is their personal orientation and professional motivation, socio - psychological characteristics, and these aspects accelerate the education of learners based on their chosen field.

The formation of an acmeological position in future teachers creates the need for a nisabatan innovative approach to the effective organization of the pedagogical process. This is directly related to the social environment. Only in a healthy social environment will progress, pedagogical-psychological factors and necessary conditions are created for the formation of a person of a comprehensively mature “akme” level.

Conclusion: in its place, it can be said that as the content of the formation of an acmeological position in future teachers, we can show that each prospective teacher will be namayan in being able to apply the acquired knowledge, skills and qualifications at a high level in practice. One of the main directions for the development of the educational system in modern society is the organization of targeted and independent activities of a person in various areas. Therefore, it is advisable to pay special attention to the content of the formation of an acmeological position in future teachers.

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